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Are We Transforming Engineers Into Vendors?

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ABSTRACT

The development of Ethics depends on the development of Values, which are shared by a given group and aids people to decide in many situations in compliance with the preferences of the same group. The Ethics in Engineering Education can, in the same way, establish the Values that need to be taught and shared by the Engineering Community. As soon as the society identifies and accept those Values, the Engineers would benefit from a higher evaluation in the society assessment. But Engineering education is suffering from the weakening of its Values motivated by private interest. Currently, the big engineering companies want to reduce the Engineer to a catalogue selling employer. In this paper, we offer the perspective of the relationship between the Engineers and their local communities.

Conference Key Areas: Ethics in Engineering Education, Engineering Skills, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning.

Keywords: Engineering Education, Ethics.

1 INTRODUCTION

The education of the new generations of Engineers is no longer a compromise between the society and the University. In the past, the society knew exactly what to expect from few branches of professions. The physicians, the lawyers and the engineers were respected by their behaviours in the applications of their specialized knowledge and skills to solve the problems of the society. Therefore, the notion of Utility was clear and the professionals were praised by this.

Some people may argue that the Professional Values of the Engineers are no longer recognized, because of having much more branches of professions and many

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specializations of Engineering. But the impact of having many different tags for the Engineers is internal: the perception of common pertinence is weakened, because the Engineers from different branches do not recognize each other. By this way, to stablish Ethics for the Engineers became much more difficult, but it is not the cause for losing the Values that were stablish in the past.

The downfall of the Ethics in Engineering is much related to the fact that the Engineers may act in different sides of the same issue motivated by the different intentions of their contractors. We may have a Civil Engineer of a Building Company against the interests of a Civil Engineer of the Supervision of Constructions of some Government. As the notions of regulation, contract and payment became much more important, the Ethics in Engineering no longer plays any role in Engineering Projects.

If we want to present to the society that the Engineers have a Code of Conduct, we need to convince the Engineers that the success in the carrier is not a matter of the consumption power they may acquire, but the solutions and well-being they provide to the society, which is the main responsible for the Education they received.

In this paper we analyse the present lack of Values in the Engineering Education and draw the attention to the fact that Engineers must become aware of the ethical and epistemic values embedded in all components of their work. It is also necessary warning the Engineering Schools to avoid the fast exposure of its own students to the interests of the Big Companies. One of the solutions is the inclusion of Ethics subject and Codes of Conduct in all the Engineering courses.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. In section 2 it is analysed the present lack of Values in the Engineering Education. Section 3 presents the interference of the big companies in the education of the engineers and the corresponding result in their professional carriers. In section 4 we present the Codes of Conduct effort many Engineering Associations conduct as a reaction to sustain Engineering Ethics. Finally, section 6 presents the conclusions and some future work.

2 LACK OF VALUES

In the past, the most prominent experience on professional Values were the “Guild” [1]. They were constituted to organize the labour, the quality and the prices of a given activity in a particular city. The “Guild” respected each other and did not compete. Internally, the members needed to obey many rules to avoid competition, to assure quality and to support the elderly. The professional Values were explicit and the notion of Justice was clear for the society.

According to Tuana [2] Values serve as a guide to action and knowledge. They are relevant to all aspects of scientific and engineering practice, including discovery, analysis, and application. She argues that ethics education should be used in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields and propose the following main groups of values:

- *Ethical values*: the good of society, equity, sustainability;
- *Aesthetic values*: simplicity, elegance, complexity;
- *Epistemic values*: predictive power, reliability, coherence, scope.

Epistemic and ethical value decisions have important social implications. This fact is reflected in the National Science Foundation broader impacts criterion and its view of the role and purpose of ethics education: “Ethics education is particularly critical to the science and engineering community as it faces an increasingly competitive funding environment; rising collaboration with international colleagues who may follow different guidelines; and growing recognition of the relevance of science and

engineering to social, economic, and ethical issues of wide public and political interest.” [3].

Nowadays, according to Chomsky [4], we live in a time where people don't think they are able to organize themselves. On the other hand, the media push people to believe the Moral Values need to fit into the constraints of the Individualism. This way, Engineers are free to compete with each other to maximize their profits and to offer lower quality for the solutions the society demands.

In this sense, the labour relationships tend to a single value: the price. But the price is the common agreement between the parts in a negotiation. For this reason, the Engineers are mostly like to worry about their propaganda, not about the quality they offer.

In this sense, according to Bauman [5], the person is the product to sell. And the Engineering title works more as a propaganda item in the curriculum vitae in the market. We only need to observe the number of Engineers in the Financial institutions to confirm that assertion. Engineers are not always aware of relevant values and ethics education should be designed to promote values identification and analysis.

3 BIG COMPANIES

The dream of the pharmaceutical industry is to transform the physician into a drug vendor. The notion of the cure has shift from a body natural process into a drug manipulation recipe. To achieve this, the pharmaceutical industry need to change the physician formation, the legislation and to make people believe the cure is not in their hands.

In the same way, the dream of the Big Companies is to have highly educated vendors, which are able to convince the local market that the only solution is to buy from its product catalogue.

As the Big Engineering Companies have money to pay more for internships and opportunities to better jobs, the Engineering students starting competing with each other. In the end, the better students are selected to earn higher incomes.

In the process, the student starts to believe in the propaganda of the big companies and in the rules of the market as the only truth behind the scenes: the competition will define their success.

The students have little access to the idea that they can help their own local communities. Those kind of problems, are left to local government only. On the other hand, the local community have little dialogue with the Engineering Faculties to present their problems. Without high internship earning, is hard to find any Engineer student.

After being convinced that about the market rules, the Engineer student, in the middle of its own formation start deciding about the disciplines to follow. At this point, the interest for high-tech products the big companies sell drives the Engineer students out to basic scientific foundations of the Engineering. They tend to follow the propaganda of the dominating Big Engineering Companies. If The Big Companies say that the future is the Storage Technology, then the students are mostly likely to search and demand disciplines related to it. In this situation, after a while, when the Storage Technology becomes commodity, the graduated Engineer will have hard times to change his/her education.

We may see, for example, in the Cisco Engineer Incubator Program in Poland, the interest of a Big IT Company on the education of young Engineers (see Figure 1). The final result of this program is to put the mind set of Cisco in the young Engineers head. The characteristics of the program is given below [6]:

Figure 1: Big Company interest on the education

- **What is Cisco Engineer Incubator?**
Special educational program designed by Cisco engineers to support young, talented students and graduates interested in networking technologies and starting the career in IT.
- **Who is it for?**
Engineering students (preferably on their last year of studies), with CCNA (Cisco Certified Network Associate) -level knowledge of networking technologies, who see themselves as professionals in IT industry in the future.
- **How does it work?**
Free CCNP (Cisco Certified Network Professional) course delivered through technical seminars and webinars between October and May, with regular office visits and meetings with our engineers and managers.
- **How do I join?**
We will kick-off the recruitment for the Fifth Edition of the Incubator Program (2017 – 2018) in Spring 2017. Please monitor this webpage for the updates on the application process and the schedule of our university events in Poland.

The notion that the Engineering work may serve to the local community and the society as a whole is weakened. Sooner as acceptable, the Engineer start thinking that his/her work may only serve to a given company, specially the Big ones. We presume Poland need Engineers to develop the country, not only to serve a specific Company for market and profit purposes.

In the end the Engineer has more short term knowledge, as the technologies evolve, which leave them in a dependency cycle on the product catalogues of a given company. They are no longer able to create new solutions. They are only able to prescribe short term solutions the big engineering companies sell.

This intentional choice is not well observed nor controlled by the Engineering Schools. The students are not prepared to recycle their engineering knowledge on top of a solid scientific foundation. The Engineer is left alone on the market with a technology mind set which is condemned to be obsolete.

In this way, the Engineer start depending more and more on the market knowledge: finance, administration, commercial skill need to be developed as fast as possible to be able to survive. The sense of pertinence to the engineering professionals is weakened this way.

The result of all this process is the loss of creativity and social relevance of the Engineer work. The Engineer mental process becomes more and more tight to the available technology culture, including the companies catalogues and the corresponding names and brands. Many of those brands are accepted as a common word in the Engineer vocabulary and are used as buzzwords.

The Engineer then is converted into a complete vendor. The Engineer can only see the society problems as an opportunity to apply all of his/her knowledge: the buzzword of big companies. The Engineer is no longer able to comprehend the society problems first, in a scientific way. He/She is only trained to search in the available catalogues, the possibility of a solution.

On the other hand, this loss of creativity and competitiveness for the local engineers represent a gain for the big companies. They have highly educated vendors with Engineer titles, which act only in the benefit of a given company, not in the benefit of the society. This is an opportunity to broaden its local market dominance as the local Engineers vendors ease the selling communication to the local consumers.

Another interesting aspect of this loss of creativity is the reduced capability of local competition. The local solutions might be a barrier for the big company dominance. But the local engineers are make to believe that there is no solution, but to buy a high-tech product made by better engineers of the big company. And the dominance is reinforced.

One of possible solutions is the use of open source software, free of charge that reduce costs and enhance engineering education with these new open source technologies [7]. With open source software, students have the freedom to put their creativity in action. It is also possible to test and modify the software, simulating real enterprise environments, which improves student's skills [8].

4 CODE OF ETHICS

Nowadays there are many efforts to establish Codes of Conduct among many Engineering Associations, for example: Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IEEE), National Society of Professional Engineers (NSPE), Engineers Australia and American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME).

One of first one's is the American Society of Civil Engineers - ASCE Code of Ethics, which is the model for professional conduct for ASCE members that is first adopted in 1914. The Code of Ethics was most recently updated on July 23, 2006. Pursuant to the Society's Bylaws, it is the duty of every ASCE member to report promptly to the Committee on Professional Conduct any observed violation of the Code of Ethics. In April 1975, the ASCE Board of Direction adopted the fundamental principles of the Code of Ethics of Engineers as accepted by the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, Inc. (ABET) [9]. In October 2009, the ASCE Board of Direction adopted the following definition of Sustainable Development: "Sustainable Development is the process of applying natural, human, and economic resources to enhance the safety, welfare, and quality of life for all of the society while maintaining the availability of the remaining natural resources."

Another example of Code of Ethics is the ACM Code that provides guidance to ACM members about committing to ethical professional conduct. The Code identifies fundamental considerations for contributing to societal and human well-being. Every ACM member who renews a membership agrees to adhere to this code, a code that was written a quarter of a century ago.

The current version of the Code was approved in 1992. This version of the Code made significant advances over its predecessor. In its role of advancing professionalism and producing a positive impact on society, the ACM replaced the previous primary function of monitoring member behaviour with an emphasis on

educating about the principles of ethical behaviour in computing and providing guidance in ethical decision making. Over the years, the Code was used as a guide to instruct students entering the profession, as a decision support tool for computing practitioners, as a standard for the public to judge the professionalism of practitioners and as an aid to address legal issues and ethical tensions. In the last few years, many questions arise related to artificial intelligence, machine learning, and robotics.

In the 25 years since the drafting of the 1992 Code began, there have been two significant, interconnected, and broad kinds of changes: 1) amazing changes in computing technology, and 2) important changes in how deeply that technology is integrated into social structures and into people's daily lives. The technical changes are substantial. The number of people impacted and the intensity of that impact have been astonishing.

In 1992 the number of people using and controlling computers seemed limited. Computers were typically in a fixed location, and were just beginning to connect via the Internet. Computers were used to print bills, to control some highly specified processes, and to guide military devices. They managed and recorded financial information, controlled some processes on our automobiles, and controlled microwaves in the air and in our kitchens. It made sense for most scholars in computing to have a narrow focus on the analysis of algorithms and a study of the resources needed to execute them. Now computing is ubiquitous—controlling our transportation and communication, and facilitating many human interactions. Computing today is in our bodies—prosthetics, pace-makers, and insulin pumps. Computing is also integral to the ways in which societies wage war. Computers impact all areas of our lives and many life-preserving functions are relegated to a piece of computer guided machinery. Many of the newest impacts of computing are invisible. Computers make decisions about who is audited, who gets a heart transplant, and who gets targeted by dangerous devices, be they cars or missiles. The changes in technology and the kinds and number of impacted stakeholders are changing society in fundamental ways.

Recently, the ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct: Draft 1 was developed by The Code 2018 Task Force and the preamble is as follows [10]:

“Commitment to ethical conduct is expected of every ACM member. The ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct (“the Code”) identifies the elements of such a commitment.

This Code includes 24 imperatives formulated as statements of responsibility. The Code is designed to apply to practicing and aspiring computing professionals. Section 1 outlines fundamental ethical considerations. Section 2 addresses additional, more specific considerations of professional conduct. Section 3 pertains more specifically to individuals who have a leadership role, whether in the workplace or in a volunteer professional capacity. Principles involving compliance with this Code are given in Section 4.

Each imperative is supplemented by guidelines, which provide explanations to assist members in understanding and applying the imperative. The Code is intended to serve as a basis for ethical decision making in the conduct of professional work. Secondly, it may serve as a basis for judging the merit of a formal complaint pertaining to a violation of professional ethical standards.

The Code as a whole is concerned with how fundamental ethical imperatives apply to one's conduct as a computing professional. The imperatives are expressed in a general form to emphasize that ethical principles which apply to computing professionals are derived from broadly accepted ethical principles.

The Code is not an algorithm for solving ethical dilemmas. Words and phrases in a code of ethics are subject to varying interpretations, and a particular imperative may conflict with other imperatives in specific situations. Questions related to these kinds of conflicts can best be answered by thoughtful consideration of the imperatives and fundamental ethical principles, understanding that the public good is a primary consideration”.

The Engineering Associations offer a high value contribution to the establishment of Engineering Ethics. But those codes of conduct are limited to the scope of a given Association. It means that they do not have the same law enforcement power as the Guild in the past. If a professional of a Guild do not followed one of the rules of the Guild, this professional is left out of the city.

On the other hand, there are many different approaches related to the different codes of conduct efforts. In this sense, the same problem of having many Engineering branches arises: the notion of pertinence is restricted to a given Association. And how can one Engineer from one Engineering Association can trust other Engineer from a different Engineering Association as they have different codes of conduct? In this way, we tend to favour the Engineers relations of the same Association. There is little explicit mention on those codes of conduct about the mutual respect among different Associations.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Engineers must become more aware of the ethical and epistemic values embedded in all components of their work as well as their significance and role in research and practice through training for values transparency and coupled ethical-epistemic analysis skills.

The Engineering Schools should avoid the fast exposure of its own students to the interests of the Big Companies. They need to understand the value of the Engineer. The society need to develop solutions for its own demands. The Engineer is the professional to offer them. The Big Companies want to maintain its own Engineering skills, reducing the local competition for solutions. The Engineering vendors maximize their profits.

The Codes of Conduct efforts represent the hope in future to establish the Engineering Ethics. But they need to grow outside the Engineering Associations limits to become an essential part of the Engineering education.

As future work we propose a study about the relationship between education and the demands of the local communities. We believe that this relationship is stronger whenever a community believes it is own responsibility to solve its own problems.

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